

Roman Science Inspired by Emerging JWST Results: [website](#), [proceedings](#), [video](#)

Session 6 live-captioning, Thursday, 22 June 2023:

[Surveys of the flickering universe and galaxy formation](#)

Patrick Kelly: Here, There, Everywhere, strongly lensed supernovae, JWST, and Roman

Let us get started. This is Session six. We are going to get a nice 25 minute talk from Supernova Refsdal about Here, There, Everywhere. Strongly Lensed Supernovae and Roman Science. Great thank you. I'm excited to talk about some new measurements. And programs are going on right now to follow up on some new discoveries at James Webb and that I am looking forward to Roman and what we might expect. And what the prospects are for science the supernovae. So, I became involved in this so we found supernova Supernova Refsdal. And we've been working on ever since. So I will talk a little bit why it's interesting. We finally come up with the measurement and a constraint on the hub of constant from the rear. The supernova restaurant. And we find the Einstein Cross here. This is the galaxy cluster. And I was in 2014 and it was predicted to reappear about a year later. And it did, and a measure of the time delay with precision and the lens model and a new independent way was discovered for the modeled galaxy clusters that are used for the models of time not graffiti with astronomy lying freezers. So, why do we care about the constant the Hubble constant? For anyone here familiar with the current tension, the local measurements using type 1A supernovae, and calibrated gives about 73. And I updated this to reach 22. And of course people could get in trouble. And then the very precise measurement comes from observation outside the cosmic microwave background. Combined with the exception of the conventional and the CDM topology. And if you put these two together, you have around 67.4 plus or minus per price act. So this is more than a phi Sigma tension and here is a plot showing a number of current constraints on the value on the Hubble constant. And here are early values from here -- and then here is a shoes the local measurements in the late measurement, and these are constraints from galaxy skills, a quasars that are multiply imaged by galaxy scale lenses. We've also heard about the measurements this morning as well. So, if you consider these most precise measurements there is a strong tension. And of course this corresponds to a true difference then is required of the revision of the standard model. The standard cosmology: a model. It's great to have independent measurements of the Hubble constant which have different systematics. And so Supernova Refsdal is a retail astronomer back in the 1960s, a gravitational lensing was served in the dark ages and this was before astronomy lens galaxies had been discovered or quasars. And that it

was an innocent let Mike that wasn't until the 70s. And so -- he did something in it interesting the article and figured out that if he can measure the appearance between a supernova and multiple energy just as you can constrain the Hubble constant. And so he envisioned a supernova and was very successful in his efforts to measure the island of Hubble Constant using the quasars. And then, finding a supernova took another 50 years. So they are simpler, especially in there like curve evolution. And so, you do not need to monitor them in for as long, also if you have a type one a supernova, you can calibrated and figure out the luminosity from the like curve, and then you can understand the degeneracy's, and then also, if we look at supernova or other objects that are stronger by clusters, the lensing systematics in the modeling systematics I separate from the existing Quasar efforts. So a little bit of background about gravitational lensing, it's always helpful, and so, from general activity you get the flexion from a point source mass, of four GM over C squared. And so lynching -- you can think of it as a source plane for the lens plane and it involves these angular Damiana bitter distances. So if you have a perfectly while lying system you that it Einstein ring like this. And if you should break the symmetry then you end up with arts. And there is the nice analogy. The optics of the basis from the wine glass. And I have optics in a very similar to those with a gravitational lens. And as you can see here they have a small line lengths and the nice rink and it breaks up into multiple arcs and these are also magnified. So, here's what we can see today. Okay, so, gravitational lensing, so if you have a piece of glass, or grasslands, you have a geometric delay and then you have it through the index of the reflection through the late passing through the glass. But instead, you have the delay from the potential with both curve space and inducing the gravitational time delay. They can then do a time delay service is the sum of these two. So I had the geometric delay in the Schapiro delay. And that's if there was no lens there at all. And from the principal we know that is a time delay surface. So you can see, the data parameter here tells you how your background source is with your lines, so if there perfectly well aligned you can see you have two extremes out here. And you can haven't Einstein ring for example, but in one dimension here you can see -- you can see the multiple images in the source. Well as moved to the Western West alignment you will only have a single -- say you're not being the strong strong lensing machine if that makes sense. So this is the expiration of strong lensing of multiple images. And then you can compute this time delay in this way, from the geometric path rank and the Lang's potential. So you can write the time delay -- in terms of the potential and if you measure a difference in the relative time delay and the difference between the arrival of two images you have doubts are too over and Delta tile for your other potential. So you can compute or infer this ratio of angled distances and the speed of light and this is important to the constant. The Hubble Constant constant. So that is what the lens model. Which gives you this potential. And that is to get to the inferences about the Hubble Constant. So Refsdal made this prediction in 1964, so there is a huge of work from a number of teams. And they're lucky enough to found the first supernova in 2016. The lunch models are very excited because it gives them a prediction about the future about when the supernova would reappear. So this is a blind test of lens model. So many of the models around the world, made predictions. So here we are in 2015 October, and it suggested that maybe should a rear. Getting concerned, however it is if you think source there, so the supernova did appear, and it was very exciting and they were able to predict the appearance of a supernova in the sky. So, we have spent the last for many of your years and has been, but the very careful analysis of modeling all of the five images of the supernova underlay curves. And it

turns out is an 87 like the supernova much like the other. So the compact gives you this characteristic slowly arising right curve as you can see here. And new reviews this as well as the deeds us if simulations we have modeled the microlensing due to stars in the cluster mediums as well as the galaxy that is responsible for the cross -- as well as mellow lensing due to the sub halos -- and measurements and certainties as well. And it's simulated the right curve and they said an air budget for the time delay. And as you can see here, with multiple imaging supernova you can get this fantastic liquor. So here we have five images and we can shift to using our measure time delays in the right curves on top of each other and you have this amazing cadence. But also is used a lot of Hubble Constant time. So, what we accomplish? Will he find 64.6 ± 4.2 . And, we have a parallel measurement using two of the models that have been previously used for any delay caused mammography. But what we've done is wait in the in the contribution of the models by their ability to reproduce the observables but do not depend on the Hubble Constant. So we look at the magnification ratios. And, and so, you get a perfect lens model and the 1.5% fractional uncertainty on the time delay will give you 1.5 measurement on the Hubble Constant. So as you might expect, the lens model dominates the uncertainty. So here's our air budget, and the cost a lot is the single largest contributor to the uncertainty on the time delay. So therefore that is the Hubble Constant. And so, depending on which of these estimates you can consider, maybe 1.8 or 1.5% retention with the local supernova measurement. So not significant, but to suggest that this is a new independent measurement and once we are able to collect a larger poll, then we should be able to come up with a new and independent constant of the Hubble Constant. To adjust the tension. In fact, it's very exciting that a stronger lens clustering supernova was discovered in the win horse pearls GTR program. Which I also have a new part of, and Brenda phi has put in a new program, so we are taking follow-up imaging of three images of a type one a supernova. And it's at 1.78. So this is really exciting, illusory able to measure its magnification from its light curve provided in the festival lens model, and that unfortunately the time delays here are allowed to be quite long. Not a year as it was the case for the other, but for months instead of Refsdal, so that should be a measured precise measurement of Hubble Constant. To people working hard on the subject. Okay, so I thought I would share some of the fairly quick calculations we did for the W WF Refsdal, so if you're able to look in the high latitude white area survey. Which will have two visits. just confirm this. Mickey should have it right. But, we should expect something like an order of 50 strong supernova to be detected. Versus the repeat visiting to detect and the second time. So -- you can only identify them after the second Epoque in most cases. But, about ten should be the cluster skill lens we be helpful for having her independent measurement from the quasar estimates. And then if you just do the square root scaling which may or may not work, you need available characterize cluster and you end up with the 2% measurement of age nine. So, I think there's a lot of promise here. Of course you would have to follow up with these discoveries. You come up with the time delays and if you have a type one a supernova that is actually not too hard because type 1A supernovas are very regular so you might not need huge numbers of observations. When there is also the higher cadence in the deeper field, and that, depending on what the area areas, you can get something from 2-8 supernovas. In either case you would have the right curves from it itself which would be nice. But if you're in the five square degrees version according to our calculations and other literature, you would only get a small number of the supernova. Okay, so now will not talk about other interesting things you can do in

the supernovae. So, they are all kinds of fun ministries we find about a more detailed today, one of them is that if you look at Baldwin and Phillips relation. In the emission lines for galaxies near the peak of star formation, then they seem to occupy different regions in the diagram in the galaxies. So what is going on? And we also would understand the population of massive stars at one and two and beyond where we can't resolve them individually except for a cluster lens individual star but so far there are a huge number of those, so supernovae provide a way to study the population of massive stars which are now responsible for the L of galaxies. One day provide the radiation and inject energy into the ISM. It also happened to be in the compact remanence of the light detection. So what might be different? Well there are eight to 12 geeky years. But what you should have is fewer generations of type 1A supernovae so you might have a great amount of oxygen around its elements from core collapse. And what could possibly explain the diagram. And probably the IMF is different. And the conditions are certainly going to be different in some ways. So, it turns out that you can actually through observation of strong lens and supernovae, characterizing details star that explodes in higher redshifts. And so, and they hereby observations that have been published of the supernovae, if they say if you can catch the explosion of the red supergiant. In the first day or a few days you can see the Black body temperature, you can see a following including as the star expands and cools. In this curve depends on the size of the supernova. Its luminosity is not yet powered by radioactivity. So the physics are simple or, you just have the shop that is heated the star, and its cooling is an expansion. And so, for a handful of events for Benny was a measure of the sizes the stars, in the nearby universe. And he subsequently exploded. So we were able to find a strongly lung supernova at the here -- there's a fourth when here, but is on top of the galaxy skill lines and so, this was a lot of fun and we made a Foss, MH -- and you can see immediately that the color of the supernova changes by I. Which is really neat. This is a single Epoque, and these images were taken within a couple of days of each other in a different bands. And through that due to the time delay you can actually see it change color over the period of days. So, we are able to fit using the model of the galaxy in the galaxy allegory was able to fit the photometry using the lens models to figure out the phase which we seem to supernova and put a constraint on the size of 600 solar radii. So this was pretty neat. We were able to measure the size of the star Nene Sow, this is with a single Epoque of imaging. So Roman should be able to find objects like this into similar types of analysis. So here are some more detailed constraints. On the envelope the mass in the radius of the generator. And they are magnified the supernovae, so we can find them, we are able to overcome -- especially will be looking for the core collapse at a higher age shift -- so we took this supernova as we just described which was a trivia cluster and use that to put constraints on the core collapse over the last red shift three. In disagrees with the number you would expect given a local way IMF and the star formation history. Whereas previous estimates from candles and clash found some discrepancy with the predictions you might expect with those assumptions. And it turns out the dust prior use was not -- but need revision. It's unclear whether the fact that that explain the difference or not. So, I think by finding magnified supernovae, it should be able to contribute to the restraints on the supernovae right? And then I thought I would end here by discussing some ongoing observations with a recent observation of the James Webb in a strongly aligned supernovae and some of the other applications of them. And so one of them which is pioneered by Steve Rodney, in 2015 was to use a type 1A supernova and imaging you can figure what it's luminosity is and figure out his

modification. And so, you can use type 1A supernovae is then new unique probe galaxy cluster models because they are one of our best tools for studying eight galaxies in higher redshifts, so they need to be indicated. And so, this is a type 1A supernova, and red shift two or three here, so this is the little red dot here. That we are using to test the lens models. And then, he is another type 1A supernova. Which is multiply image and discovered part of a snapshot program. But we caught the chanting image of the supernovae. And so we are not able -- as can be tough to do. And they're going to put constraints on the Hubble constant, and they're working on that. But in any case, what else can we do with these will be can get that with James Webb. In detailed analysis of the individual type 1A supernova and their very helpful because for type 1A cosmology whether the population of type 1A's scene for how it is similar or different from that we see in a higher shift. So for some evolution in the earlier evolution you might expect it of course. Begin examine them with higher resolution spectra with James Webb. Okay. So, I think from the highlighted wide-area survey, we should detect a large number of men supernovae. In a significant fraction should be some group and cluster skill lenses so hopefully we can put these to work. And if there is a fairly large high cadence area, we can also get like curves from Roman itself to measure time abilities. So strong lens and also as a tool for measuring the supernova rate in higher redshifts. And you get the natural boost from that certification. Due to the time delays and we can construct their early like curves are supernovae and put direct constraints on the size exploding. And then they are exciting neutrals for constraining galaxy cluster models.

Awesome and perfect timing. There was a lot in that top so maybe we'll start with a few questions in the room and see what we got online. Yes? Thank you for the very exciting results -- and perspective. This is from MIT -- I apologize but you mentioned there lens supernovae and amine type 1A supernova itself can be a standard Novi Nikki Newman measure? And with the lens it can measure it in another way. If you try to compare the results from the supernovae like the resolve in the event's how the Hubble Constant? Again I apologize if I missed a very, very in this comparison. Should be take two or three more questions or I ready to sit down? Come and take -- the your audience wants to ask you a few more questions. I don't know for set up online yet? Do we have one more question for Pat? Yes I miss the talk but I read the paper. So, how does it work in general because this can be future lens like this, will we have a lot of different models and they predict a large range of -- what you think going forward when they get out large range of Hubble constant results. In this case, you have a large range, some some bottled or accounting and some are not. But what we do in the future when you have a large range? Of the Hubble constant? Well, yes, our approach as you share, in the paper was to wait the model according to their ability to reproduce -- and each independent variables, the murder of their identified as being successful and also the ones that were most successful in the simulated question the simulation done by then and get, so there's an agreement there. So, we have learned something as well, the parameter models which has perceived most of the weight and are most successful. So we his new supernova we said that we need to get those models going on that. And so -- in some cases they might not be enough observables to do this exercise again. Here EF3 Mrs. They make images as to five, and so yes I think it is -- Would you exclude some miles ahead of time because they didn't fit it well? Going forward how are you going to decide which models get a vote? Were talking about this yesterday, may be another simulation

effort, assuming this only willing to step up and do that, it could be another worthwhile exercise for sure. But yes, in the meantime we can wait by the observables yes that is a wonderful question. All right let us say thank you to Pat again. Especially under these adverse circumstances.

Aaron Yung: Guiding future deep-wide Roman surveys with galaxy formation physics we learn from JWST

And now we have Aaron Yung. Thank you. So I am Aaron Yung. And I'm coming in to space telescopes in this fall, today I'm going to you about Guiding future deep-wide Roman surveys with galaxy formation physics we learn from JWST. It's almost like a copy that after the conference title. To have the sticking your head a little bit more, with someone randomly tells you why they really want a Roman ultra deep Field, some of you here to -- let's kick off with some of these results. Some part of the Sears team, which is the earliest team to receive data that was taken back in June last year. So almost all year end, but within the first three months, I made a slats of recap the things that happened earlier on, so those are pretty designed survey we have a lot of things for everyone. And we looked at mythologies for stars and nearby galaxies in they were not previously available with Hubble. And there we found very crooked this extremely distant guided leaks -- for the first few minutes after getting half of our data. And it's really nice and exciting. So for a recall from yesterday's talk, it's one of the early programs those has a \$17 to cover over the EGS bills. It's a big team of 150 people, and we got data early on, so now we have all the data. Let's take a look at what we found. So we have this data on the early look on the five which put together a of how the galaxy formed. In as I've mentioned this before, Macy's galaxy, there's an even deeper program where I had 50 overs over hundred and 20. We were able to take a look at the faint end of the undersea function of the measure through nine through 12. We also took a step of my theory, and I didn't make these observation myself and I wondered if there were measured at high resolution pricing. ? Okay, another thing that we found is that there are a lot of a GM out there, either obscured or embedded nearby or far away, villages all over the place. So the theme there seems to be with these red dots and everyone is talking about. Extremely different galaxies is through the red dots. Every seal out more of them in the future. And it tells us a lot about the deep universe. This is what a doctor from the press release Dave with the Roma communication teams release back in March. So G ESPN Hubble have this review, and this is a representation of what was seen through the telescope. This is what we made for a two square degree field, but the galaxies are not color-coded or size coded for how big they are but they're not representative but they illustrate that. But if we do a random pointing in the universe, we could have lent is on the field that was full of galaxies, the field that doesn't contain too many things in the left. This is totally possible. But with Roman, we can have a panoramic view of what's happening in the universe. And you can go out to survey a big patch of the sky. It's not really just faster, but we can actually do things that cannot be done with Hubble. So in this press release, they say that if we were to survey this two square discrete field it would take Hubble over 85 years. In Roman can do it in just 63. Which is nice. So please let's do this. It's not just that, so we've been drawing the slides to illustrate how the universe have evolved a could have evolved over time. This is not based on the simulation let's go check it. But is not just about logical structure in the year by universe, but we can actually study how long

they can over the long period of time going from Russia ten down to six. Are there for. You can pull out the whole picture and how the universe is be involved in this. Okay, so in theory plays an important role in modern day service. Back in the original field it was great. We will just wait a long time for to show up. Nowadays we need to optimize the survey and justified to the tech that the survey will return a lot of science. I had time before we even did the survey years before the service you created simulations of the universe. So we can do all such of experiments on it and forecast what would come out of the service. So with what we just saw with the Sears team, we make them into mock images which emulates what you really see in the universe. We see this is a weblike region. And have they see the universe instead of using a fox which held most most simulations are created. From the field get Jacob Orr realistic stick a gun realistic galaxies that we can draw from past surveys over we can make these Mark Fields more realistic and use them to practice the reduction of a carving surface that we put it. From there we design the survey and multiple iterations of it. And with certain survey designs were to change the outcome? Make it look better or worse? From there we are ready to go into the observation and we saw all these amazing galaxies and only ask a question do they match the simulations. Are they what we expected? If they are what do we have right? I'll be right for the wrong reasons and more likely we didn't get it right? Maybe they're more red smudges than we expected -- so we ask ourselves what is missing in their current physical model of the a lot of things missing -- so let me show you what's missing since this is a very short talk. So this is a summary flow chart for what goes into the model -- we start with the dark matter halo's. And then we track multiple thing goings-on in these hills. How many hot gas and how much is able to pool at the coal gas and then how is converted into stars, then we stocked feedback and other things and then we model positive evolution back in the overtime that we can do this really efficiently. We can do millions of galaxies overnight in. So this is due to be updated and we have a pipeline that converges the physical part properties into surgical properties like luminosity in your favorite instruments -- a full spectrum and also admission lines. So looking at the physical processes that are in there, there are a lot of things missing as I've mentioned in the air, and really, these are things that we should be investigating with the JWST with the next three years. update the physical model so we can make them better for Rome and use them how to guide how Roman can do a deep survey and how they can get out of there and how we can officially survey a Roman feel their work on a you need in future rations do you need. So for example when working to see first thoughts were Roman Navy, and they really serve a wide area, but this thing is, having this in place will help us understand over time, licking check the model from observation so you can't see the physical processes. It was feedback we can constrain their observations wintry we anchor this part wrong some of these are in place. In that we can make predictions for four objects and things that happens to massive halos. The prefecture from Rome and it would you wait five years to see how wrong we are. So right now we have a placeholder model that was very well but we are seeing it everywhere, so will probably have to do something about it and people will be talking about this lately. So we've explored some of these potential model modification in the paper that was printed down in the corner. I don't have time to get into the full details, but right now there's no new models being created since the results came in. A lot of people are recycling and insisting model is a Jodie Meeks at the bit will work. Those who will see your new models to get developed to see which one will come right up. Okay. So this is the same view you saw is just not too many galaxies. And they're not that

big in the real side this is just a representation in the cartoon. But it's on the right, these are two corrosion functions. A new expectation is the smallest Gladys Moorcock clusters and then there are less clusters. But I wanted to show you if we can measure clusters four to 4.5, in the field that is the size of the Hubble field. And we do this a hundred times it's all over the place we can't do it it'll just be too small. And we know that, this is just an extreme to illustrate we can't do it. But will be marketed to bigger and bigger fields, dreaming about this field -- this is about the size of existing Hubble or -- you will get better of course. But mostly because these fields are small. But we just have 1.0 which is a two square degree field you can see visits to get a lot better if they go out to do bigger and bigger fields. You will want to repeat what Michaela showed as yesterday, but the fact that he did his single experiments with the function. It's really important in there to get these prints right. There is a cartoon -- but it hasn't worked that way. But okay. So I'm wrapping up now. It's not just for Roman. But we're bringing this project to the universe. This brings exploring synergy to the universe -- in we have asked to be on their free advertisement. There is a lot of Institute supply this paper science. But thank you.

All right we have a question for Aaron Yung in the room. Okay, I'm curious about what you think will be the first black hole change he would make in the models because I guess for a long time you change your models to the luminosity functions. Right, we let the physics to the evolution then we compare it to see if the modeling works. So right now at the top level he is on we put it in a one and it doesn't matter and then we just let it accrete. We explore the scenario of a massive scenario, or a mixed scenario, and then we also implement an update -- in fact we do that with the growth mechanism. So we can do a lot of controlled experiments in control of them to other more detailed simulations, or incoming observations. You will see if we were able to produce all of that. But we can't model every step because we don't learn anything from it. But we'll see if we can reproduce observations or costs the range. In the mood and get something right. That is our hope. Last call -- any more questions? All right then let us think Aaron Yung yet again. [Applause]

John Wu: Representing cosmic structures with graph neural networks

Our next talk will be John Wu representing cosmic structures with graph neural networks Okay. Can you hear me? Let us see. All right. We'll thank you very much, good afternoon, my name is John Wu, and I am an assistant astronomer STScI. I had a pleasure working with Roman for half the time. But I'm not good to talk to you about that, the other top of my the other half of my time here I thought creatively about new lines of research that provide data-driven images. So what you want to think outside of the box, this is not going to be a tried-and-true technique for this is going to be an interesting new set of methods that will revolutionize our field. And that's where we were going to shine with Roman. So here is an overview of galaxy evolution and they were going to talk a little bit about the context and why we want to study galaxies with Roman in the sense and then when I talk more about this message. Okay, cool. So thank you Aaron for setting up the stage and thank it's all the speakers, then the really wonderful in describing the many different types of signs we can do, so we know from theoretical simulations the early times in the universe you have dark matter because getting down. And they're sitting this large cell structure we see here. Of course the baryons will constitute the galaxies. But we really just need

to pay attention to the fact that galaxies are in the skilled environments. In their environments that we want to probe how influential they are in raising and leading to the formation of these galaxies. It is important that we study each of these different components. So it takes a village to raise a galaxy as I stated on this title, it's tempting to look at them in isolation, or to look at them very specific areas, but those dedicated observations are important as is the big picture view. In symptoms and we see beautiful images like these, we see this image a few times even this afternoon, this show needs are going to get this spectacular view of galaxies and other surroundings. So obviously this very deep field and many other lensing cleansers provide opportunities to study not just the distant universe but also galaxies when they're in the environment. So I think being able to do time domain science and using it to constrain cosmology, and to study galaxy evolution -- you can almost look at the graveyards of galaxies and where they go and how they live their lives up to this point. And JWST is revolutionizing our field here. But that only represents the tip of the cosmic iceberg. We are looking at these very dense regions in large cell structure. You may prove we also want to get a glimpse of how the surroundings of these stars play a role. So, to that point, we know that that is going to give us a much, much larger view, so if you look at this cluster we can look not on the scales of 1 degree, and I can say this is for Leica campaign here, you get one square mega parsec. But for the Roman instrument, you can get a much larger -- so this enables us to think about how data-driven scientist will revolutionize the field. So again, to say this again, we are not looking at the most massive parts of the galaxy clusters but we could really go out into a totally different the genes in more diverse work environments and seen them in very different ways and we can go and study those. All righty, so a related piece of work that I'm not going to talk about now is that especially even at low redshifts we are still learning a lot about the dim galaxies out there. It would hurt bit about those surface brightness fluctuation is a new tool to go and get some stellar populations and we can really study results and you are now showing galaxies that are in the 4200-parsec range that we see with the traditional sky survey and going out with that 17.8. In this confirm that this is what a map of a good chunk of sky like before -- essentially before an analysis and now is when I use a particular data-driven technique to rely on them more further galaxies to distinguish between nearby galaxies from distant interlopers contaminants. But this is a program called an example of which were using the dock energy spectrum to follow up using spare fibers on that highly spectral graph to go and find these and think galaxies and confirmed the redshifts he can see the dramatic increase that we can get in the substructure. To that end, I now want to switch gears, and talk about how it can use the constants of galaxies surrounding and a better effort of surrounding the halos in the galaxies. So bear with me now, but were just gonna take a look into graph theory will readjust representing the ball and stick model. And we have that are new, and galaxies can be seen as nodes is our vast medical graph, and the separations between them can be thought of as edges on this graph. Okay? So this is just from the simulation box. And it's actually a sub region and there is zero. So is he displaying around, we can also do things I try to simulate things from projection affects operational effects of some level of realism. But the point is that we really care about the fact that they are these galaxies there in these roast structures called sub halos, some of the sub halos of the route to an apparent halos and we can take advantage by linking them together on mathematical graph. Okay so then what you do with that? This is slightly more realistic ration of this data set and what it should look like and whether they decipher how massive they are. And

they showed a chapter on randomly as a function of this surface mass density. Obviously we can make this better. But the point is when we simulate observational effects and realism we can then go and try to teach new networks that live on these graphs how to basically connect the galaxy properties with the halo properties. And so, for example for galaxies we can measure or take measurements in the catalog form of the positions velocity and in this case this is not just a 2D projection affects various OXY in the radial velocity by the line of sight velocity. And then the stellar mass, then from that we went to see how well we can actually recover the dark matter halo mass. And in order to do this we ask to turn them into a linking link. And they can pass messages to each other pitch which he wanted to think about that is basically some constant effective field from each galaxy emulating out Akyah Miranda. In they use a mirror magic in there that we about but we want to see if this approach works. So it kind of does, this is a certification of what we typically think about in the distribution modeling, is a tried-and-true theoretical approach, we actually find that you can recover the halo mass here, this is true versus the predicted one, until about .3 dense and a mass range. But the scanner is actually much reduced or even a two dimensional dimensions, when you take advantage of this environmental dimensions, here's the stinging graph -- anyway, the point is that these galaxies knew something about their neighbors, and they have is this forces from them. An astute title interactions into other sort of physics, it's actually interacting in ways that are not captured simply by modeling galaxies into a observation. So that's why we think these graph neural networks to such a better job of recovering the mass care. We can do also to further interesting exercises here. Trying to see where the galaxies are connected in an effort to see what is the optimal sort of message passing length. And that might tell you something about clustering skills and the sudden mass ranges, but a lot more Tessier needed. The kind of remarkable thing to me is that these two deep -- you can do the full thing in 3D Blu-ray know the position of the velocity of everything, but that 2D version of this is not that much worse. Because you actually get a lot of projected stuff and a lot of say in all this junk which is contaminating. You actually also can probe really far out in the world beyond the radius effectively. And they do a good job of taking the pencil beam information that goes beyond, the sky you one medical parsec out yet to go 50 miles upright 60. We can then effectively within information and contentment observation hands and use it to your advantage. So to to trade data-driven technique here. The last plug here, they showed up this morning, but we can do the inverse mapping is well, we can pay galaxies on the Sam Hill, so if you're interested in doing things in the halo occupation distribution, we also find that this is worked out with Christian that you know this approach really outperforms a sub halo abundance method of using machine methods which are tried-and-true in the state-of-the-art up until now. We do much better here, so check the paper out is just on the archive as of this morning. Okay, so lastly, I just want to say and reiterate, no amount of time, but we've been seeing the tip of the iceberg here at JWST, at the tip of the cosmic iceberg as we target the frontier field, and also the Lenton clusters, now we can garden seated aversive I am a diverse cultures and galaxies evolve thank you.

Really cool. Is there a question in the room? This is really cool stuff. I was worried about these sort of machine learning things will train them on the physics we know, and the large share of speaking to with halos. But is there a risk that was sort of teaching and what we know now and how we use it to discover new stuff or rediscovering the same stuff that we already know? Yes

thanks. I think that is a really good way to frame some of the perils of machine learning which is why are we doing this every trying to get it physics and if the writing of the physics they were covering the -- I mean there are some things that we don't know intrinsically which is what is the actual dark matter content in these galaxy clusters on the larger field? So I think what it does give us is an act dog general direction we can compare other things. And I think that through these different methods we can really see whether or not they are useful new ways of representing or even whole paradigm shift in how we want to think about galaxies. For example you can imagine being built on merger Tria model where you can take full advantage of the additional information of galaxies. So when -- we know that with those models it varies depending on how much you care about your neighbors and get distance is still the galaxies. But in this sense you can involve them and connect them to make them know about each other. Two can be stepped up in the three theoretical domain as well. So here's a quick question from us. So when you show the graph the notes, you can use other graph methods to understand the evolution of the intricate structures between them what are your thoughts on that? Yes so you certainly can do that. Again may be -- so repeating what Karen's question was about is that we really do want to see what kind of physics we can learn so when we think of this message it's something to see all the different ways they can be expressed in the representation areas and this certainly interesting areas there that might seem more interesting to an astronomer. But I'm open to suggestions. great talk John. In the example you showed us, with the uncertainties on the quantities and I guess the more general question is can you use this technique to help hold the observing strategy for example if you chose to put more time into the spectroscopy and drop one filter would you be better off and getting your death of the mask as I type of question two -- As for the latter I am not sure I think it would be a with the endeavor to form a question they are concerns taken but we can do is add scatter and that is actually useful for training their networks because that's the level of robustness. One other thing is that I would say that one of the really nice thing is that they really efficient and they really, really easy to run and they must easier to train in accomplishing all that sort of thing. So we could run through many stipulations quickly and I think that's another power. The thank for that question. Think you know we are out of time.

Ali Ahmad Khostovan: Let's go extreme with Roman, observing $z \sim 0.5-2$ low and high EW ELGs

Lets go extreme with Roman take it away. All right -- as the title said, this click stream with Roman. What I mean by a stream is going for a wide range from low to high for the night like galaxies. Specifically the emitter. So in this presentation I will be talking about how we use an approach to measure and constrain the distributions from 0.4 to 2.2. And how we can use that to infer what we could potentially see in a Roman prism survey. Is there a push button somewhere? Let hello. So with JWST it's been a year now that we've been on, and we been getting a lot of data on lot of cool results that are popping out of this. One in particular is that we are finding a pretty interesting extreme universe in the sense that compared to the lower cosmic noon even we are finding these really H alpha emitters and star formation rates. in these are equivalents to thousands of Ångströms. And that these objects are also on the low mass end. When you put it together these types of systems are pointing towards star-forming active Lomas types of galaxies. And people have been investigating these added time. In the JWST world. We

had to give them the access study. But the thing that we figured out in that time. Was that there is this anti-correlation between equivalence and civil mask that these Lomas galaxies tend to be the one that has a higher quickly win for all -- and the typical wind also increases with red shift in any given stellar mass. But the thing is how much or how well to the really constrain all of this one in particular is how the selection biases affect the way that we measure the equivalency with distribution emitters. Could it be that things are actually overestimated due to selection biases along so release of this idea that we really need to constrain that equivalent with distribution in order to truly understand how these things evolve and what the underlying correlations are and how we can use it later on to forecast what we potentially can see in the other surveys. So nothing to counter that much detail on this given the time I just checked -- but overall, our approach is to create an intrinsic sample that is basically set by this one parameter right here. You didn't see it throughout the rest of the presentation is basically the scale factor in the exponential distribution. Another way of thinking of it is the typical equivalent went from pulling from zip on going from 0 to infinity and the distribution. Louis King on this is that we then tried to mark a survey by simply being filter effect in the nature of the filter. In applying selection functions that are similar to the data sets with enemy comparing to and these are all selected samples. You may get this at the end as an observation on Mark sample that simply sets by whatever nod we provide in the initial step. And then be compared to equivalents distribution that is inside the lock sample with thieves observation data. And we say that -- but is not legal whips and we go back and we verify with that knot is innocent and we get to some conversions. And the result of her getting here is that there is still at this in change it now so that the selection is corrected filter in the equivalent with correlation. The slopes are shallower compared to what we've previously gotten, they are still there and they are statistically significant. In the other thing is that the slope increases as you go to a higher one as well. So it's about minus 0.8 here and then minus 0.2526 if the measurement. So essentially what it means is that the Lomas galaxy, the ones that are actually getting the most significant evolution compared to hi's galaxies and we can see on the right-hand side, how the typical cliff but wins so this is from most the time and it goes from ten Ångströms to almost nearly a hundred Ångströms B on two. Once again your notice that this block kerf which is an intrinsic measurement is below below these observations appear. But, if you were to apply all the limits that we find in their new survey what that actually bumps everything up to the blue line here that matches with the observations as well. So seems to be that not including the selection corrections or changes the way that the measurements for typical equipment wins but, it seems to be more of an organization difference. Overall, you'll be hearing me say this over and over again, that is essentially the primary translation that we used to describe not only this into court correlation for the mass but also this evolution as well. And we will use that to infer some information and also for the information you sure you all at the end. So using this change it influence and evolution model, we use it to see if this model will actually reproduce a luminosity function. Which is basically all of these -- things that you are seeing here compared with observations. Which are the solid symbols, but also the prison from 2015. So seems like things are pretty much lining up. And this is able to predict the equivalent and what the luminosity function will also be like it any measurement. So they can take the information in taking one step further and say what types of emitters are really the important ones when it comes to star formation activity at different time periods of the University's history. And so the plot on the right, that's doing this star information rate of friendship, and the blue

curve is what you get for the observation and squares going all the way to the edge of two, and the different curves are for different equivalents with limits. So one thing we've noticed is that once you go beyond .5, it seems to be that the really high equivalent team emitters, they seem to be contributing a lot to the total star-forming budget of the universe. What I should go towards lower red shift, it starts to change. But the thing is, do overall importance and we see from this is that these high equivalent highly coveted T systems beyond 1.5 seem to be quite important if you already seen how we are getting systems and how the equivalency are well above the hundreds to thousands of Ångströms as well. So really it points to these high equivalency systems being pretty crucial. And they also primarily Lomas galaxies based on their winds could very adversity as well. So besides that effects one, not only a height of important for the star formation activity but it can also be very important as well so they have looked from that proton's efficiency. And how his skills were still immersed in the equivalency win. That the Lomas in high equivalency seems to be pretty important when it comes to measurements of 60 ions which basically tells you how much I have some photons are produced and send out to the universe. Consider not also has a star formation important, but a click the some of the choices that we are going after for that organization. So then how chemical after I promised to have? 20 seconds oh gosh -- so how quickly can explain this? We basically get a lot of sources with women. And -- with Ronan, we can get a wide range of equivalency wins. But I would really appreciate you said ultradeep, I see the survey as well. Because if we push the line limits even more, we get some of those really, really Lomas high equivalent went with nova chip of two and .5. I would save over this with a quick question with a look at five times ten minus 18. You can really start to fill in the area over here and there will enables us to look at objects in detail and also seen at high redshifts. Thank you.

Do you have any questions in the room? Okay. So wonderful I love this. So I was wondering how are you dealing with the extinction corrections? Yes so this is one of the uniqueness also with that equivalency -- but it comes with this caveat as well. If you assume that they are equivalent, and there is debate on that as well, but those corrections would cancel out essentially because you have the line folks which is affected and you have the equivalency was is also affected in those two effects would cancel each other out, but if it doesn't you have an extra factor there as well. So in the people writing on this. There is a description on that as well. Hopefully I can get the archives.

Mingyang Zhuang: Characterization of JWST NIRCcam PSFs and implications for AGN+Host image decomposition

Okay so this is going to be about host image decomposition with Roman. Okay take it away. Roman you hear me? Okay, hello, everyone, I'm collaborating with JWST, I would have to thank everyone for giving this opportunity to present my recent work. So it suggests that there is an important ruling evolution showing at the left figure by the gas reservoir. And it's a little bit more difficult. In the moments into the flow of the center. Both processes can inject energy to provide a self-regulating feedback. In its also acquired by them to reproduce conduits. Shown in the right figure, similar to the supernova feedback, it use to reduce the efficiency of cultivating variance into star in agencies that are required to reduce the efficiency at the highest scale

mass end. With the high correlations with the host balance deck Alex Alex galaxy. Due to the difficulties of obtaining dispersion people have focused on the scale 96. Well, they if greatly improve the image in terms of sensitivity and resolution in the coverage. So what I show in the right figure is the comparison between the resolution and the range and the improvement in terms of resolution. And he can only compare the unique optical with resolution. While it can cover all the way from the infrared. In this improved resolution is crucial to understand the structure and also to study the feedback inside the galaxy. So no task is perfect, and that is a constant in dependence on the focal plane so does the near can also have this effect. For example they used filters to find out that there is a picture take variation in the 150 filter. And they find that the maximum variation happens in the shortest wavelength and it can be up to 15 to 20% in the 90 image. They also found out that there temporary variations which is near 4%. However they are working on the images of the individual exposures. In we are focused on the drill image. So actually we see the images come into use. From my work, we use archival images as the cells continue. But what is special about this is that it has starts and they could be serious issues about blending. We use three quotes to construct it. One is based on stocking stars and others is based on a pixel based model. All the images have a common scale -- for pixel, in the drizzle image is an image where we measured the science measurements. We select the highest signal into a six by six. For the variation. So, in general we have two types of models for each code, a global one and a regional one and we have one PSS, and one extra model for PSS X. So first we tried to select the best PS FX to construct the model and reuse the mosaics and we use it to construct the models based on the sky scale and the magnitude differences select the best one. And for most of the sources, they reduce it and pick up one will be fine better performance for the mottos of PS F. Especially for those bright sources. Newly freed neglected to measure the only has it in the small-scale. So using the best performance we use the models from this code to study the spatial variation. So the PSF models shows the actual images so first if you look at the global surface brackets it's actually quite similar in shape. But if you look at the residual we find there significant gradients up to 100% in this variation continues towards a larger radius dominated by the larger radius. This table summarizes the PSF models at different filters. In a different region. And we find that the maximum variation is trying to find the shortest wavelength. In the differences is the at 3%. The right figures shows the distribution and the pattern. The access ratio. We find the PSF. Those patterns could be affected by the PSF during the process. And then starting the imaging, generated a large amount of agents in the range of agents house ratio. For each agent, three different PSFs. Generating those. A broad one and narrow one. PSF mismatch. In terms of the results to other fields, other tests. So first we used this to study the effects. The figure on the right shows, compares to a difference in terms of parameters versus the host magnitude. We find it's mainly affected by the host ratio, not the whole structure. We find the higher systematic basses, systemic bias, larger scanner, a larger uncertainty of host parameters. We find host magnitude can be measured close to the depth. N can only be measured 2 or brighter. We investigated the effect of PSF mismatch. We used two. One is 4% broader and the others 44% narrower. We find similar results. When the agent starts to become brighter and brighter. No matter the PSF is broader or narrow, it leads to overestimated holes. For the broader PSF it's mainly due to flatter hosts. For the narrow model, more concentrated. The overall performance for the narrower PSF model is much worse. I will skip to the Roman PSF. Very large field of

view. Significant PSF variation across this large field of view. The figure shows the center and the other boundary. The difference between the two types of PSFs and the features are quite different. Actually the final PSF depends on the properties of the combined images. Dithering and the footprint. In order to gather accurate sampling of the host, spatial and temporal. That's it. Thank you.

There's not a lot of glory in digging into the details of PSF so good for you. I think we have time for one question. Yeah. Going to have to wait for the mic. Okay, great. This is Matt. I like your talk. Definitely diving into the details of the PSF. You talked a bit about the systematics and the scatters that you get from assuming a global PSF and the magnitude scatter. I was wondering, did you take a look at the astrometric scatter, scattering the positions of the stars? What systematics would you induce by not taking into account spatial variations? For the stars? yet, positions of the stars resolve the magnitude shifts in scatters. Whether positional shifts? Center position. We haven't checked that. There's a lot of folks interested in astrometry. I would be interested no systematics. Thank you again.

Caitlin Casey: Anchoring future Roman deep fields with COSMOS-Web: large scale structure to transients

We are going to have our last... There is Caitlin, online. Nice to see you. Nice to see you. Can you guys hear me? Great and we see you but we don't yet see your slides. Caitlin: That's what I'm doing now. All right. Take it away. Caitlin: Cool. It's great to be there. I'm sorry I couldn't be there in person. I'll get to that in a bit. I'm excited to share with you today a bit about the cosmos web program. Touching on a little bit in the discussion of extragalactic. We have a lot of goals in COSMOS-Web. Today I just want to touch on some of the goals that I'm not used to talking about a lot. More focused on large-scale structures and more off-the-wall goals, including transient science. I will dive writing pad I will point in that in the background, it is some of our data, the initial data that we got. 4% of our map. We are panning and zooming into that 4%. We have now much larger data set. We are still not finished obtaining data. COSMOS-Web, just give you some context if you're not familiar with it, it's a 255 hours cycle program. The largest GO program. Led by myself and Jeyhan Kartaltepe. It involves a lot of people. I really want, before I dive in, thank the folks who have done a lot of the lion's share of work on COSMOS-Web. On the imaging side, Max Franco. Here at UT Austin. Daizhong Liu. They have really made sure we have the highest-quality images images we can have. Our catalog team lead by Louise Paquareau and Marko Shuntov. Making sure we are leaving no stone unturned. In the alphabet soup of all of the extragalactic D fields, I want to remind you or introduce you to the COSMOS field if you don't know what it is. On the left-hand side we have a bunch of to scale schematics of well-known deep field in the literature. Some of the candles fields. To scale against COSMOS. COSMOS is the entire field of view. It was the single band HST program acquired almost 20 years ago now, which is astounding. But we are doing with COSMOS-Web is coming back with four filter near Camp coverage in a smaller field of view that inside within COSMOS. Half square degrees in the middle of the cosmos field. This is how our depths compared to other JWST D fields. We are the shallowest but by far the widest area serving. With NIRCcam, we have four filters. Shallower than jades but significantly larger and we also

have coverage in the near range. This is being a Roman and do diversity conference, COSMOS-Web is at the juncture between deep small field JWST surveys and Widefield shallower surveys. We hope that COSMOS-Web is really useful to the Roman community. This is what the exposure map will look like when we are totally finished. We have a good chunk of data but not all of it. Blue is our NIRCams exposure map and that is contiguous over .54 square degrees. And the other exposures are parallel, MIRI. They are in orange. More scattered. We obtain the first set of data in January. I am showing you these babies here because a funny coincidence for me is that I gave birth to these twins within the same 24 hours as we obtain our first data after years and years of waiting. Of course, that happened and has led to a very, very busy and sleepless year. But it's been fun. We obtained half of our data more recently, in April of this year. We have been working on it seriously and we are waiting for the other portion more or less the other 40% that hasn't been taken yet. In the northern half of the field. It is worth pointing out that in black, that data, there is data that's been already taken as part of the primer survey embedded within COSMOS-Web. I'll get back to that point in the moment. Everything shown here in dark blue we have on hand. It happens to be 0.28 square degrees, one Roman field. It's a happy coincidence as well. When we are finally done with COSMOS-Web, it will be three times larger than all other JWST deep fields combined and that really provides a unique way to investigate science it would not be possible in other deep field surveys. The time I have left, I'll describe our goals, weak lensing goals to calibrate and anchor the stellar mass-Halo mass relation. Mapping to the EOR. With the first science school and I think there's been really interesting discussion of this already. Good links to Roman goals as well. The fundamental need to understand the relationship between galaxies and their dark matter halos. We want to understand how it assembles in dark matter halos and how it changes and evolves with time. Such tremendous impact on the huge sweep of observations that we obtain. And so coming out of that is of course the stellar mass to halo mass relation. We of course infer stellar content directly through starlight and want to easily infer the mass of the larger dark matter halo around a given galaxy. That's often done through the stellar mass to halo mass relation. It's worth 20 out that the stellar mass to halo mass relation has no Buddha constraints -- has no good restraints. If you want to measure the mass of any object there are two really good ways of doing that. One is kinematics. It's often done through satellite galaxies. Of course with the surface dimness, that becomes difficult. The second option of course gravitational lensing. Strong lensing is great but those are fairly rare although we are finding new strong lenses in COSMOS-Web so we are excited about that. Weak lensing becomes really the bedrock of how we make this measurement. So with JWST at a given redshift we'll be able to infer the distribution of stellar light. By measuring the shapes and orientations and careful deconvolution of the PSF, we can infer the distribution of dark matter. Use it to anchor the relation. This is directly dependent. We need the density of background sources. Its unique territory for JWST. To show you the range of what we will be able to constrain. Solid lines, the different colored measurements of the relation. Redshift of 1 using the existing HST data in COSMOS. Some simulations suggesting that there could be slight evolution as well out to higher redshifts but that hasn't been observationally constrained. We will be able to do that with COSMOS-Web. Redshift of 2.5 or so. Excitingly we will be able to start to break up the stellar mass to halo mass relation evolution with baryonic observables. We will split up galaxies. Start to piece together the difference in the stellar mass to halo mass relation and it can help us in turn the mechanisms

better. The second goal is mapping large-scale structure out to the EoR. It's where COSMOS-Web is well-suited because it covers such a wide area. I'll speed up. We don't know the dominating sources of re-ionization. Very different views. Re-ionization bubbles in the literature in terms of simulations and COSMOS-Web can really start to map large-scale structure. Not only discover the brightest galaxies but also map the environments in which they live. I want to show you in that 30 seconds some interesting really cool discoveries we have from our new data. Extremely luminous sources being found that are brighter than GN-z11. We are excited about that. The very last goal is searching for high redshift transient. We are excited about this. Difficult problem. This plot shows you expectations of how bright parent stability supernova should be in their light curves. Based on hydrodynamic simulations. You see these sources could be brighter than the 28th magnitude for something like the year to three years. That would be deductible in something like Cosmo's web. A beautiful byproduct of the cycle one decisions happy accident is that because we have another survey embedded in COSMOS-Web, we've been able to stagger our observations by a year so we will already have a year sampling cadence for two different data. After 5 microns. That's really excited. Roman is where this will really be transformative. albeit at slightly lower redshift but that's where we can realistically follow up. I will stop there. Thank you. Caitlin? A lot in there. Caitlin: A lot. Yes. And congratulations on your twins. Caitlin: That's why I'm not there. We have a question in the room. We have one online. Let's start there. It's a question. What's the background galaxy density you expect to constrain Halo masses? Caitlin: That's a great question. We calculated that the threshold had to be something like ten per square arc minute above a redshift -- at about a redshift of 4 per week lensing measurements. That's about what we'll get. The depth of the survey roughly reaches 28th magnitude in the LW filters. Sorry, I should have clarified. Ten per square arc minutes we would also be able to do reliable measurements for. Not the lowest signal noise sources. Something exceeding 15 or so. Have you looked into similar estimates for the predictions, TD supernovae. Caitlin: Of course, of course. Not in great detail, no. I would love to learn more. That is not my area. It's not really the expertise of the majority of the COSMOS-Web team. We are really excited to see the potential of time domain science. Roman. Let's think Caitlin -- let's thank everyone for the sessions. A great set of talks. One more round of applause. We are going to do a few poster sessions. We'll start with a video recording. There are no questions after the posterior lightning talk as they are supposed to be short. However, we are strongly encouraging that you put the questions on Slack so that people can communicate. While we are setting up, take the opportunity to announce again we would love to have your thoughts about the topics of discussion that were discussed yesterday on Slack. However format you want them to be. Please delegate someone, a synthesizer for your session. Ideally someone who would be available on Friday to present the summary of your talk and the summary of the conference. Final announcement. The dinner is kind of choose your own adventure portion. On the slack, their arson suggestions of restaurants in the area. Some may have a local person if they were able to sign up for it. If there is no local person that signed up for it, then you are on your own. Hopefully it will be fun and enjoyable. Shouldn't be that busy. So that's the end of the announcement. Looking to the first poster. Hello, everyone. I am Wenxiu Li. The distribution of the ratio. We can connect with observable and constrain our model. It's constrained by the Q LF evolution. Here I am showing the model. Redshift from 4 to 7. We overlaid the detection limit. We can see Roman is especially sensitive. Obscured fractions. We

can model the black hole growth which reproduces both the luminous quasars redshift higher than 6. We predict the early evolution of black hole and the stellar mass of their host galaxies. Close to or over massive local real auction. Our poster describes these findings. You're interested, please check it out. I'm joining remotely and happy to have any discussions with you off-line. Thank you. Hi. I am Rachel Beaton. Happy to represents someone who is currently on the other side of the earth so if you have questions, go to slack. He's good at answering them. We been working on surface brightness fluctuations of nearby galaxies. Thinking about how to detect them. Using Roman to follow-up. Not fully resolved. From that we are trying to figure out if we can use the combination of the optical and infrared to get a distance to the objects so we can get physical sizes and also do inferences on the stellar populations. The plot on the other side gives you the forecast. If we can make everything work. You can find fake galaxies. Somewhere between 20 and 50 parsecs would be kind of fun. If you have any questions, go ahead and forward those to Jiaxuan on Slack. We are really excited about this. I will also do my poster. But for the pandemic, I worked a lot on H not how to measure distances. It turns out the stars that have good parallaxes from Gaia have bad magnitudes in the infrared. Two mass saturates really quickly. We are building a telescope on the loading dock at Steward right now. Very exciting. It will observe in the near infrared on the optical at the same time. Dual being with a splitter in the middle that shoots about the same field in both telescopes. It's meant to go on its own and monitor bright stars. We are happy to hear about other interesting and fun science cases we can do with this it's meant to be easy and run in our free time once we get it up and going. You can send those questions to me and I'll probably send you to Andy, the engineer. Knows all the details. And then think Andrea. Ray, you'll be next. Thank you. My poster is, as Jenny put it this morning, and infomercial for massively multiplexed spectroscopy. That can be achieved from the ground with the Roman Grism with some complementary capabilities. The main motivation for this is to understand how of secured AGN, the red dots. The -- how they grow supermassive black holes. The poster includes nearby luminosity and infrared galaxies with optical. Including one with dual AGN system that's imparting matter into the medium. A work led by a conference attendant. Luminous type 2 and type 1. 158-micron cooling line. We are trying to understand how the ISM is being shaped by the quasar. All of this will be revolutionized. PSF, each band, double the fibers but with a line, timeline of the 2030s. Thank you. Hi, I am Ray. I want to say a quick note about Vera and Nancy. 38 years ago more or less when I started here, I used to sometimes sit beside Nancy Grace Roman. I didn't know that was her. I didn't know where her role was but she was a very important person in the development of Hubble. I also worked with one of Vera Rubin's postdocs on galaxies. She was always very nice to me, very glad both of them are getting the kind of recognition that they have long deserved. They deserve more. Okay. Back to the poster. I won't belabor the fact. Roman is the same size as Hubble in terms of the mirror. We are not going to be breaking the mold with new high-resolution morphologies at ZF ten. Okay. I guess we have to go out again. Everybody back almost? I promise I didn't hit any buttons. Should I go ahead? Do you want me to wait for just a bit? Okay. The way things are going. Anyway. As I was saying. Roman has the same size mirror as Hubble. The morphologies are very faint, extended material with high redshift galaxies won't be at strength. But we be able to go quite deep. It won't do the same kinds of morphological studies that Hubble could do which are still very impressive. Combining that in terms of the large-scale structure and going deep which is something that I would really like to

see that people have also mentioned here. Okay. Going deep. In terms of imaging. The spectroscopy. It will be a great thing. That is something that's probably the main conclusion of my poster really. Roman deep fields will be valuable compliments to the JWST wide and shallow fields. I should've also said we would like to add these deep fields. We think it's important to consider joint optimization between Roman and Webb. Also considering other multi-wavelength observatories. A Roman ERS program will be very valuable. In all honesty I am a member of the CEERS team so I have that perspective. In terms of providing processed data scripts, all kinds of things. We think it will help give the community a very good start on what's really possible with Roman if we can do deep wide fields. Have that data be given out to the community. As a measure of the impact of things like this. We've got -- we have a publications page. 30 papers submitted. Published. The community has about the same number. It's a big impact in terms of informing the community about what's really possible. I'll stop there. Thanks.

Thank you so much. It's coffee break time. I've been poster viewing. Correct? Yes. And then at 4:30 we have our public lecture which is going to be pretty special because we have someone who is very close personal friend of Nancy Grace Roman to give us a bit more about her. And then I'm going to talk about the mission or something. So it should be really fun we hope it's going to be fun to have a more public talk to and a pretty intense science today. Please go enjoy refreshments. Look at posters. We'll see you here at 4:30 if you're staying here for the public talk. Thanks.

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

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